

LEGAL ANALYSIS OF NORMATIVE ACTS REGULATING THE JUDICIAL STATUS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article analyzes the history of the development of normative-legal documents related to the status of judges in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the significant changes made in this field. The formation and improvement of the normative-legal framework regarding the status of judges are divided into five stages: the first stage – from independence until September 2, 1993; the second stage – from September 2, 1993, to December 14, 2000; the third stage – from December 14, 2000, to July 28, 2021; the fourth stage – from July 28, 2021, to August 21, 2025; and the fifth stage – from August 21, 2025, to the present. At each stage, the main rules concerning the status of judges were thoroughly analyzed, and their legal significance was studied. The article aims to identify the development processes in this area and demonstrate their place within the legal system.

Keywords: status of a judge, constitutional foundations of the status of a judge, rights and duties of judges, main guarantees of judicial independence, requirements for candidates for judgeship, judicial oath, maximum age for holding judicial office, procedures for the election and appointment of judges.

The judiciary is an integral part of any legal and democratic state, playing a crucial role in upholding justice, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens, and ensuring the rule of law. The independence of the judiciary, in turn, is closely linked to the clear and firm legal definition of the status of judges. Therefore, improving the system of normative-legal documents related to the judicial status and studying their stages of development is of great scientific and practical importance.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation of the judicial system and the legal foundations of the judges' status have gradually developed during the years of independence, reaching a new stage through consistent reforms. The Law "On Courts," adopted in the early years, was aimed at ensuring the independence of the judiciary, while subsequent normative-legal acts further strengthened the legal, social, and material guarantees of judges' activities.

The study and analysis of the adoption and development stages of these documents reveal not only the evolution of national legislation but also the

consistency of the state policy aimed at ensuring the independence of the judiciary. From this perspective, the scientific study of the development stages of normative-legal documents concerning the status of judges, as well as identifying the strengths of the existing system and areas that require improvement, represent an important scientific and practical task.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms are being implemented to ensure the independence of the judiciary, to develop a corps of qualified personnel within the judicial system, to improve the system of selecting, training, and appointing candidates for judicial positions, as well as to strengthen public confidence in the administration of justice.

In this regard, **the analysis of the formation and developmental stages of normative-legal documents concerning the status of judges** in our country is considered to be of particular scientific significance. The study of this process makes it possible to gain a deeper understanding not only of the legal foundations of the judiciary but also of its constitutional principles.

The analysis of normative-legal documents related to the judicial system should, first and foremost, begin with the **Basic Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan — the Constitution**¹. As a result of the nationwide referendum held on April 30, 2023, the new edition of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan further strengthened the legal foundations of the judiciary in the country. **Chapter XXIII of the new Constitution** embodies the provisions related to the judiciary, encompassing **Articles 130–140**, and clearly defines the constitutional status of the judicial system.

It should be particularly noted that **Articles 132, 134, and 135 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan** are directly related to the status of judges, and these constitutional norms are consistent with the direction of our research.

In particular, **Article 132 of the Constitution** determines the procedure for the formation of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to this provision, *the judges of the Constitutional Court are elected by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan upon the recommendation of the Supreme Judicial Council, based on the proposal of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, from among qualified specialists in the fields of politics and law, with the participation of a representative of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.*

¹Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/-6445145>

In addition, the Constitution stipulates that *the judges of the Constitutional Court are appointed for a ten-year term without the right to re-election*. The Court also elects from among its members *a Chairperson and a Deputy Chairperson for a term of five years*.

Article 134 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan clearly defines the procedure and terms for the appointment of the leadership of the Supreme Court. According to this article, *the Chairperson of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan and his or her deputies are elected by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis upon the proposal of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for a term of five years. At the same time, the constitutional norms establish that the same person may not hold the position of Chairperson or Deputy Chairperson of the Supreme Court for more than two consecutive terms*. This restriction has been introduced to ensure the rotation of leadership positions within the judiciary, to promote renewal within the system, and to strengthen institutional stability.

Furthermore, **Article 135 of the Constitution** defines the procedure for the election of the leadership of the Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Under this article, *the Chairperson and Deputy Chairperson of the Supreme Judicial Council are also elected by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis upon the proposal of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for a term of five years. Likewise, the Constitution stipulates that the same person may not serve in these positions for more than two consecutive terms*.

These constitutional norms serve to ensure the organizational independence of the judiciary, promote transparency in the appointment of judicial leadership, and uphold balanced and democratic principles of governance within the judicial system.

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, one of the important steps taken towards the establishment of the judiciary and the creation of its legal foundations was the adoption of the Law **“On Courts”² (No. 924-XII) on September 2, 1993**. This document served as the main normative source that defined the organizational and legal foundations of the judiciary at that time.

Section IV of this Law, entitled “Status of Judges,” consists of three chapters that define the legal status of judges, the principles of their professional activity, and the guarantees of their independence:

1. Judges, their rights and duties;
2. Main guarantees of judicial independence;

² The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Courts” No. 924-XII, adopted on September 2, 1993. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-425?ONDATE=29.07.2021>

3. Material and social security of judges.

The first chapter, titled “Judges, their rights and duties,” provides a detailed explanation of the unity of the judicial status, the requirements for candidates for judicial and people’s assessor positions, the procedure for the election and appointment of judges, the judicial oath, as well as their rights and obligations. In its substance and purpose, this section served as one of the most important legal foundations for strengthening the legal status of the judiciary, introducing unified principles within the judicial system, and ensuring the independence of judicial power.

The second chapter, entitled “Main Guarantees of Judicial Independence,” establishes the key legal mechanisms aimed at ensuring the independence of the judiciary. This chapter, in particular, stipulates a strict prohibition against interference in the professional activities of judges, provides for the application of liability measures for showing disrespect toward a judge, and consolidates the legal foundations of the principle of judicial immunity. In addition, the chapter sets out the procedures for suspension and termination of judicial powers, the grounds for disciplinary liability, and the rules governing the activities of judicial qualification boards. These provisions serve to ensure the practical independence of the judiciary, to protect judges from any external influence, and to strengthen the principle of inviolability in their professional activities.

The third chapter, titled “Material and Social Security of Judges,” outlines the measures related to the material provision and social protection of judges, as well as the support extended to their family members. These provisions are designed to ensure the stability of judicial activity, to create social and economic guarantees for judges to make independent decisions, and to enhance the prestige and authority of the judiciary.

On December 14, 2000, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Courts”³ was adopted in a new edition and entered into force as Law No. 162-II. This document represents an important normative-legal act aimed at further improving the organizational and legal foundations of the judiciary, strengthening the institution of judges, and ensuring the independence of judicial power in the country. Section IV of this Law, titled “Status of Judges,” encompasses Chapters 7, 8, and 9. It should be particularly emphasized that although this Law lost its legal force on July 29, 2021, it left an indelible mark in history as a significant stage in the process of reforming the judicial system.

³The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 162-II of December 14, 2000, “Oh Courts.” <https://lex.uz/docs/-68532>

Each chapter of this Law highlights different aspects of the judicial institution. In particular, **Chapter 7, entitled “Judges, Their Rights and Duties,”** consolidates the main provisions defining the legal status of judges. This chapter includes the following provisions:

- *the general concept of judges;*
- *requirements for candidates for judicial office;*
- *the status of people’s assessors;*
- *the procedure for the election and appointment of judges;*
- *the term of office of judges and the procedure for its calculation;*
- *the term of office of court chairpersons;*
- *the judicial oath;*
- *the rights and duties of judges;*
- *the maximum age limit for holding a judicial position.*

Chapter 8, entitled “Main Guarantees of Judicial Independence,” contains provisions aimed at implementing in practice the constitutional principles that ensure the independence of the judiciary and the inviolability of judges. This chapter establishes the following key provisions:

- *mechanisms for ensuring judicial independence;*
- *application of measures of liability for showing disrespect toward a judge;*
- *prohibition of interference in the process of administering justice;*
- *procedure for the fair distribution of cases among judges;*
- *judicial immunity;*
- *procedure for suspension and early termination of judicial powers;*
- *grounds for bringing judges to disciplinary liability;*
- *powers and procedures of judicial qualification boards.*

These provisions serve to ensure the institutional independence of the judiciary, to prevent external interference in the adoption of judicial decisions, and to safeguard the inviolability and professional reputation of judges. Thus, this chapter consolidates mechanisms that guarantee judicial independence not only from a legal standpoint, but also from organizational and ethical perspectives.

In addition, **Chapter 9 of the Law, titled “Material and Social Security of Judges,”** sets out the provisions concerning the material support and social protection of judges, as well as measures to support their family members. Furthermore, this chapter provides for the maintenance of social guarantees for judges after the expiration of their term of office, including the procedures for ensuring their pension rights and other social benefits.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Courts” ⁴ (No.703) was adopted on July 28, 2021, and represents an important normative-legal act aimed at further improving the organizational and legal foundations of the judiciary in accordance with modern requirements. This Law, comprising a number of chapters and articles, comprehensively defines the legal framework of the judicial system.

Chapter 8 of this Law is directly related to the topic of this research — the status of judges. The chapter, entitled “**The Status of Judges, Their Rights and Duties,**” elaborates on the following key institutions:

- *general provisions concerning judges;*
- *the status of people’s assessors;*
- *the judicial oath;*
- *the rights of judges;*
- *the duties of judges.*

This chapter establishes the fundamental principles of judicial activity, the professional responsibilities of judges, and the system of legal guarantees aimed at ensuring the independence of the judiciary. Through these provisions, the Law seeks to strengthen the status of judges, align their legal position with international standards, and create the necessary conditions for the administration of fair justice.

In our opinion, **Chapters 9, 10, 11, 12, and 13 of this Law** are also directly related to the status of judges, as they contain provisions defining the organizational foundations of the judiciary, the independence of judges, the procedures for disciplinary liability, as well as their material and social guarantees. In this regard, these chapters also require separate scholarly analysis within the framework of our research.

In particular, the chapter titled “**Fundamental Guarantees of Judicial Independence**” sets forth essential provisions ensuring the independent functioning of the judiciary. This chapter enshrines constitutional principles such as guaranteeing the independence of judges, establishing liability for contempt of court, prohibiting interference in the administration of justice, and safeguarding the immunity of judges. These norms are designed to ensure the practical independence of the judiciary and to enable judges to perform their duties free from political, administrative, or other external influences.

In addition, the chapter of the Law titled “**Election and Appointment of Judges**” defines the requirements for candidates for judicial positions, the

⁴The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Courts” No. 703, adopted on July 28, 2021 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-55349>

procedures for electing and appointing judges, the process for appointing court chairpersons and their deputies, the term of office of judges and the method for calculating it, as well as the grounds for transferring a judge to another judicial position. These provisions are aimed at establishing a system for forming the judicial corps based on the principles of transparency, fairness, and professional competence.

The 11th chapter of the Law is devoted to the disciplinary liability of judges, providing for the grounds for such liability, the procedure for initiating disciplinary proceedings against a judge, the types of disciplinary sanctions that may be imposed, and the procedure for appealing decisions regarding disciplinary measures. This chapter serves to ensure professional discipline among judges, strengthen their responsibility in the administration of justice, and enhance public confidence in the judiciary.

The 12th chapter, titled “Suspension and Termination of a Judge’s Powers,” sets out the grounds for suspending a judge’s powers, the procedure for early termination of judicial authority, as well as the rules concerning the powers and activities of the Judicial Qualification Boards. These provisions aim to ensure the stability of judicial status, prevent unjustified removal of judges from office, and at the same time, establish a lawful mechanism of accountability in cases where a judge commits a violation of the law.

Furthermore, **the 13th chapter of the Law, titled “Material and Social Security of Judges and Their Family Members,”** outlines the provisions concerning the material support of judges, their annual paid leave, the procedure for providing them with housing, as well as measures to ensure the social protection of judges and their family members. In addition, this chapter establishes guarantees granted to judges after the expiration of their term of office, the application of labor legislation to judges, and the rules regarding their pension provision. The legal guarantees enshrined in this chapter are aimed not only at ensuring the independence and stability of judicial activity but also at strengthening the social protection of judges and enhancing the authority and prestige of the judiciary within society.

It should be noted that in regulating relations related to the status of judges, not only legislative acts but also subordinate regulatory legal documents play a crucial role. In particular, **the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.4570 of October 4, 2013, “On Measures to Improve and**

Enhance the Efficiency of the Activities of District and City Courts,”⁵ holds significant importance in this regard. This decree contributed to the improvement of the human resource policy within the judicial system, including the enhancement of the procedure for forming the judicial corps.

According to the Decree, the age requirement for candidates for judicial positions was increased, and a mandatory condition of having a certain period of legal work experience was also established. These changes were aimed at enhancing the professional capacity of the judiciary by attracting highly qualified, experienced, and mature legal professionals, thereby strengthening public trust in the administration of justice.

In regulating matters related to the status of judges, special significance is attached to the **Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.4096 of January 6, 2019, titled “On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the System of Training Candidates for Judicial Positions, Retraining Judges and Court Staff, and Enhancing Their Professional Qualifications.”**⁶ Based on this resolution, the system of training, retraining, and professional development for judicial personnel was fundamentally reformed. As a result, new mechanisms were introduced to enhance the professional competence of candidates for judicial positions, equip them with modern legal knowledge, and elevate the overall professional level of the judiciary.

In addition, **the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.6034 of July 24, 2020, “On Additional Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Courts and Enhance the Effectiveness of Justice,”**⁷ served as an important legal basis for strengthening the institutional foundations of the judicial system. This document also introduced certain provisions concerning the status of judges and their professional activities. In particular, it stipulated the abolition of the Research Center for Judicial Practice Issues under the Supreme Judicial Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Supreme Court, and the Higher School of Judges under the Ministry of Finance.

The implementation of these reforms marked an important step toward institutionally optimizing the judicial system, eliminating functional duplication, and strengthening the independence of the judiciary.

⁵ The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4570 of October 4, 2013, “On Measures to Improve the Activities and Enhance the Efficiency of District and City Courts.” <https://lex.uz/docs/-2255026>

⁶ The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.4096 of January 6, 2019, “On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the System of Training Candidates for Judicial Positions, Retraining Judges and Court Staff, and Enhancing Their Qualifications.” <https://lex.uz/docs/-4141425>

⁷ The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.6034 of July 24, 2020, “On Additional Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Courts and Enhance the Efficiency of Justice.” <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4910826>

It should be particularly noted that, under the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.6034 of July 24, 2020, a significant task was assigned to the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Supreme Judicial Council. According to this decree, these bodies were instructed to develop a new version of the Law “On Courts” and submit it to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan by November 1, 2020.

✓ The draft law is intended to include a number of provisions aimed at improving the functioning of the judiciary, strengthening the legal status of the judicial institution, and further enhancing the institutional independence of the court system. In particular, the draft law envisages the following issues:

✓ clarifying the structure of the courts, as well as the jurisdiction and powers of district (city), inter-district, regional and equivalent courts, along with the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its judicial panels, Presidium, and Plenum;

✓ establishing the requirements for candidates for judicial positions and for incumbent judges;

✓ clearly defining the procedure for the appointment (or election) of judges, court chairpersons, and their deputies;

✓ strengthening the status of judges and enhancing guarantees of their independence;

✓ improving the procedure for judicial disciplinary liability, in particular by introducing a mechanism whereby disciplinary proceedings may be initiated only by judicial qualification boards;

✓ setting out, through clear legal norms, the grounds and procedures for the suspension and termination of judicial powers;

✓ improving the system of material support and social protection for judges.

As a result of the implementation of this directive, the newly revised draft Law “On Courts” served as an important stage in the further reform of the national judicial and legal system, ensuring the genuine independence of the judiciary and enhancing the effectiveness of the administration of justice.

In addition, **the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.141 of August 21, 2025, titled “On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the System of Training Highly Qualified Personnel in the Field of Administration of Justice,”**⁸ is also one of the key normative legal acts aimed at improving the preparation of candidates for judicial positions. Based on

⁸National Database of Legislative Information, August 23, 2025, No. 06/25/141/0772.

this Decree, the Academy of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the Supreme School of Judges under the Supreme Judicial Council.

A systematic study and analysis of normative legal acts related to the status of judges show that the formation and development of this institution have gone through several important stages. The improvement of the legal framework governing the judiciary and the status of judges has served as an integral component of the reforms aimed at strengthening the independence of the judiciary and ensuring fairness and transparency in judicial proceedings in our country.

Based on the above, the development of the normative and legal framework regulating the status of judges in the Republic of Uzbekistan can be conditionally divided into the following stages:

The first stage — from the declaration of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan until September 2, 1993. During this period, the initial steps were taken to adapt the legal foundations of the judicial system inherited from the former Soviet Union to the national legal system.

The second stage — from September 2, 1993 to December 14, 2000. In this period, the Law “On Courts” (No. 924-XII) was adopted, which for the first time defined the legal norms concerning the status of judges as an independent legislative act.

The third stage — from December 14, 2000 to July 28, 2021. During this stage, the Law “On Courts” (No. 162-II) was adopted, through which the institutional and organizational foundations of the judiciary were improved, and the legal status and guarantees of judges were further expanded.

The fourth stage — from July 28, 2021 to August 21, 2025. In this period, the new version of the Law “On Courts” (No.703) was adopted, marking a new phase aimed at ensuring the independence of the judiciary, strengthening the legal status of judges, and enhancing their social guarantees.

The fifth stage — from August 21, 2025 to the present. At this stage, the Academy of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the Supreme School of Judges under the Supreme Judicial Council. Starting from October 1, 2025, an entirely new mechanism for training candidates for judicial positions has been introduced. In particular, six-month professional retraining courses in judicial specializations have been launched at the Academy, implemented on the basis of state grants.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/-6445145>

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8. National Database of Legislative Information, August 23, 2025, No. 06/25/141/0772.

